

On the Representation of Time in the Brain

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Abstract

In this note, the author suggests the presence of frequency-specific metric¹ cells in the brain. These cells are hypothesized to be sensitive to gravitational wave signals initiating in different epochs of universal history. This hypothesis leads to a novel definition of time travel.

If time is discrete, and the brain is receiving metric information from all different ‘time-eras’ of universal history, the brain is all the time getting a certain overall signal which has several frequencies in it. This happens partly in the visual-electromagnetic domain but primarily in the metric domain as shown recently in [1]. Metric perturbation signals beginning in different time eras may have different frequencies associated with them, perhaps in part due to the stage of universal expansion at that point. Just as rods and cones in the human eye are frequency specific, we may hypothesize the presence of frequency-specific metric cells in the brain, sensitive to different universal epochs. We may imagine that there may be a preference or selectivity of certain time-eras over others, and adaptation too. In this sense, time travel is nothing but the selective activation of specific groups of these metric cells, which then inundate the brain with information and details from that era.

References

- [1] Aman Chawla and Salvatore Domenic Morgera. Computer study of metric perturbations impinging on coupled axon tracts. *Physics Essays*, 36(2):160–167, 2023.

¹Metric is used here in the sense of General Relativity where metric perturbations are also known as gravitational waves.